

Review Article

Comprehensive Review on Clobetasol Propionate, Neomycin Sulphate, Clotrimazole As Topical Preparation: Role in Dermatitis

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Dermatitis was a broad term used to represent a range of common illnesses characterized by itchy skin irritation. However, the term eczema is frequently used interchangeably with dermatitis, despite the fact that it refers to atopic eczema. Dermatitis results from a complex interaction of environmental, immunological, and genetic factors. Another prevalent factor that contributes to dermatitis is a family history of the ailment, which might enhance an individual's chances of having it. Certain genetic differences may cause the skin to overreact to environmental stimuli. Dermatitis can take many various forms, each with its own set of traits and triggers. Dermatitis can be classified into several categories, including atopic, contact, seborrheic, and nummular. The report was intended to discuss the types, causes, symptoms, and management.

Keywords: Clobetasol Propionate, Neomycin Sulphate, Clotrimazole, Topical Preparation, Dermatitis.

INTRODUCTION

Dermatitis, sometimes known as eczema, is a prevalent skin disorder affecting millions of individuals around the world. It is characterized by skin inflammation, which causes redness, itching, and discomfort. Dermatitis can take many different shapes and severity levels, and it can have a substantial influence on one's quality of life. Dermatitis results from a complex interaction of environmental, immunological, and genetic factors. Another prevalent factor that contributes to dermatitis is a

family history of the ailment, which might enhance an individual's chances of having it. Certain genetic differences may cause the skin to overreact to environmental stimuli ^[2]. Dermatitis is a common, long-lasting inflammatory inflammation of the skin with a variety of signs and symptoms. It explains the peculiarities of a specific skin condition. Also known as an eczema. Most disease episodes (80%) begin in childhood or early childhood, with the balance occurring later in life. The worldwide incidence is between 2% and 10% in adults and 2.7% to 20% in youngsters. ^[3]

Image No 1: Image of Dermatitis

Pathophysiology of Dermatitis:

Mostly affected to the skin protective barrier. The skin barrier gets damaged. Skin barrier is getting weak and the allergens enter to the body through the skin. The outer layer of skin which is epidermis is normally protects our body from the allergens such as dust, other chemicals and germs. When this layer gets weak or damaged because of some harmful chemicals or allergens the harmful substances can easily enter to the skin. Once these types of substances are enter into the body, the immune system in which (T-cells) are present they can identify them as a harmful and it gets start an inflammatory reaction so that can release of such chemicals like, histamine, cytokines and prostaglandins. After these chemicals introduce into the body reactions such as swollen, itchy skin, redness are occur. If exposure continues for a long time, the skin becomes thick, dry and scaly due to continuous inflammation.^[4]

Symptoms:

White people are more likely to have dry, cracked, and scaly skin.

- Rash on swollen skin, color varies based on skin color.
- Blisters, possibly with oozing and crusting.
- Dandruff.
- Thickened skin.
- Small, raised pimples are more common on brown or black skin.

Causes of Dermatitis

To comprehend eczema and its etiology, it is necessary to recognize the distinctions between healthy skin and skin afflicted by eczema. The skin comprises a thin, protective outer layer (the stratum corneum), a superficial layer containing skin cells (the epidermis), a middle layer (the dermis), and a deep layer of adipose tissue. Every layer of the skin comprises adipose tissue, epidermal cells, and moisture, all of which contribute to the protection and preservation of skin health.^[5] Healthy skin cells are plumped with water, creating a protective barrier against infection and harm. Fats and oils in the skin help the body regulate temperature, prevent hazardous substances or bacteria from entering the body, and allow the skin to retain moisture. The exterior skin cells are like bricks, while the fats and oils in the skin are like mortar that holds everything together and acts as a seal. This means that skin cells attract and retain water, while fats and oils aid in this process^[6].

Treatment of Dermatitis:^[4,5]

Dermatitis medication differs by its severity and type, but usually involves topical medication, modification of habits, and measures to self-care. Treatment include glucocorticoid cream, gel, or ointment. In creams or ointments, use hydrocortisone as well as clobetasol, neomycin sulfate, clotrimazole. Clostar-Gm, Terbinaforce-Plus NF Cream, Clop-gm neo cream

Light therapy, commonly referred to as phototherapy, is a further possibility. Exposing the itching to controlled levels of artificial or natural light.

Image no 2: clop-gm neo cream

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Reported HPLC Method of clobetasol propionate:

Sr. No	Title	Description	Ref No
1.	Development and Validation of a Fast RP-HPLC Method for the Determination of Clobetasol Propionate in Topical Nanocapsule Suspensions	Mobile phase – methanol-water (80:20 v/v) Stationary phase- λ_{max} – 241 nm Linearity- 5.0–40.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	6
2.	HPLC determination of clobetasol propionate in cosmetic products	Mobile phase – water-acetonitrile (40:60, v/v) Stationary phase- 5 μm Purospher-Lichrocart column λ_{max} – 237 nm Linearity- 0.1-2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	7
3.	A Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Nadifloxacin and Clobetasol Propionate In Its Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	Mobile phase – Acetonitrile: Water (50:50) (% v/v) Stationary phase- C18 Shim pack XR ODS II column λ_{max} – 242 nm Linearity- 1-12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	8
4.	A novel HPLC-UV method for determination of chlorocresol, clobetasol propionate and miconazole nitrate in cream with environmental impact assessment	Mobile phase – Buffer (0.05 M KH_2PO_4 sol.): Methanol (32:68, v/v) Stationary phase- Agilent C_8 (150 mm length \times 4.6 mm ID, 5 μm particle size) column. λ_{max} – 223 nm Linearity- $R^2 \sim 0.9999$	9
5.	Forced degradation studies of clobetasol 17-propionate in methanol, propylene glycol, as bulk drug and cream formulations by RP-HPLC	Mobile phase – methanol: water (68:32 v/v) Stationary phase- Nova-Pak® 4 μm C_{18} 150 mm \times 3.9 mm id cartridge column λ_{max} – 239 nm Linearity- 0.15–15 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$	10

Reported HPLC Method of Neomycin sulphate:

Sr. No	Title	Description	Ref No
1.	Qualitative Analysis of Neomycin in Virtue of HPLC Estimation	Mobile phase – (Methanol: buffer; 60:40) Stationary phase- C18 column λ_{max} – 290 nm Linearity- 10-60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	11
2.	Green RP-HPLC Stability-Indicating Assay Method for Neomycin Sulfate in the Veterinary Formulation	Mobile phase – (Methanol: buffer; 60:40) Stationary phase- Kromasil C18(w) λ_{max} – 210 nm Linearity- 40-200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.	12

3	Determination of neomycin and related substances in pharmaceutical preparations by reversed-phase high performance liquid chromatography with mass spectrometry and charged aerosol detection	Mobile phase – (water, methanol and heptafluorobutyric acid) Stationary phase- C18 Hypersil® Gold aQ column λ_{max} – 210 nm Linearity- 500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	13
4	Stability indicating method development and validation of Beclomethasone dipropionate and Neomycin sulphate Ointment using HPLC with microbial assay.	Mobile phase - ACN: WFI: Methanol: Glacial Acetic Acid: Triethylamine (55: 40: 5: 1: 0.1 v/v) Stationary phase- Kromosil C18, 5 μ , 15cm x 4.6mm column λ_{max} – 235 nm Linearity- 5-15 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	14

Reported HPLC Method of clotrimazole:

Sr. No	Title	Description	Ref No
1	development and validation of stability indicating hplc method for clotrimazole lozenges formulation	Mobile phase – (Methanol in (25:75 v/v %) Stationary phase- Gracemart C18 (250mm×4.6mm, 5 μ) column λ_{max} – 215 nm Linearity- 0.5 to 60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	15
2	Development and validation of HPLC method for determination of clotrimazole and its two degradation products in spray formulation	Mobile phase -acetonitrile and water (65:35, v/v) Stationary phase- .5 μm Zorbax® SB-Phenyl column (75 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., Agilent Technologies). (250mm×4.6mm, 5 μ) column λ_{max} – 210 nm Linearity- 0.1-2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	16
3	Development and validation of a reversed-phase HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of clotrimazole and beclomethasone dipropionate in lotion and cream dosage form	Mobile phase - acetonitrile-water (70:30, v/v) Stationary phase- . Kromasil C18 λ_{max} – 254 nm Linearity- 0.1-2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	17
4	Development and Validation of Stability Indicating RP HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Beclomethasone Dipropionate and Clotrimazole	Mobile phase - ammonium acetate: acetonitrile (10:90 v/v) Stationary phase- . Hi Q Sil C18 (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μm) column λ_{max} – 223 nm Linearity- 10-60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	18

Reported UV Method of clobetasol propionate

Sr. No	Title	Description	Ref No
1.	Development and validation of UV spectrophotometric method for quantitative estimation of clobetasol 17-Propionate	Solvent- Ethanol λ_{max} - 239 nm Linearity- 2 to 40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	19
2.	spectrophotometric determination of clobetasol propionate in pharmaceutical preparations and environmental samples	Solvent- Methanol: Water (80:20) (v/v) was used as a solvent λ_{max} - 240 nm Linearity- 2.5 -30 $\mu\text{g/ ml}$	20

3.	formulation and evaluation of ethosomes of clobetasol propionate	Solvent- Methanol λ_{max}- 239 nm Linearity- 1-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	21
4.	combination effect of luliconazole and clobetasol for treatment of skin ailments	Solvent- Methanol λ_{max}- 312 nm Linearity- 5-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	22

Reported UV Method of Neomycin sulphate

Sr. No	Title	Description	Ref No
1.	Indirect determination of neomycin by derivative spectrophotometry	Solvent- methanol λ_{max}- 277 nm Linearity- 0.102-0.510 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	23
2.	Study Self-association, Optical Transition Properties and Thermodynamic Properties of Neomycin Sulfate Using UV-Visible Spectroscopy	Solvent- distilled water λ_{max}- 270nm Linearity- 0.102-0.510 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	24
3	Rapid analytical procedure for neomycin determination in ointments by CE with direct UV detection	Solvent- chloroform λ_{max}- 200 nm Linearity- 0.102-0.510 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	25
4	Chemometric Calculation for Determination of Betamethasone and Neomycin Mixture in Cream Supply by Ultraviolet Spectrophotometry	Solvent- ethanol λ_{max}- 240 nm Linearity- 170 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	26

Reported UV Method of clotrimazole

Sr. No	Title	Description	Ref No
1	Spectrophotometric and spectroscopic studies on charge transfer complexes of the antifungal drug clotrimazole	Solvent- Acetonitrile λ_{max}- 396 nm Linearity- 1.00–25.00 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$	27
2	Eco-friendly ultraviolet spectrophotometric methods for the determination of clotrimazole and tinidazole in bulk and ointment dosage form	Solvent- ethanol λ_{max}- 370 nm Linearity- 17.5 to 32.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	28
3	extractive spectrophotometric determination of ketoconazole, clotrimazole and fluconazole by ion-pair complex formation with bromothymol blue and picric acid	Solvent- chloroform λ_{max}- 415 nm Linearity- 3-60 $\mu\text{g/ mL}$	29

Management of Dermatitis:

It should be emphasized that dermatitis does not always have a definitive cure. However, appropriate skin treatment can help control symptoms and improve the quality of life for those plagued by the illness. Here are some strategies to consider: Moisturizers and emollients are vital for keeping the skin hydrated and strengthening the barrier. Topical corticosteroids are frequently used to treat inflammation and irritation during flare-ups ^[30]. In

management of dermatitis, identifying and avoiding triggers that worsen dermatitis is very vital. Using hypoallergenic goods, avoiding known irritants, and making changes to one's environment can all help to reduce allergy exposure. Good skin hygiene, using gentle cleansers, having moderate baths, and wearing breathable clothing can all assist with dermatitis symptoms. In severe dermatitis, a dermatologist may give oral corticosteroids or immunosuppressive medicines to decrease inflammation and provide comfort. Light therapy, often known as phototherapy,

is the controlled exposure to ultraviolet light while under medical care. This can alleviate symptoms by lowering inflammation and delaying skin cell proliferation. Stress can exacerbate dermatitis, thus stress-reduction strategies like meditation, yoga, and mindfulness can help with symptom management [31].

Diagnosis of Dermatitis:

To help you get an accurate diagnosis, your doctor will most likely perform a physical exam and review your medical history. In rare circumstances, a dermatologist can determine the type of dermatitis just by looking at the skin. If there is cause to believe you may have an allergic reaction to something, your doctor may recommend allergy testing. In some circumstances, you may need a skin biopsy to determine the cause. Other tests, such as skin swabs and blood testing, can aid in the diagnosis of your dermatitis.

Differential Diagnosis:

There are several alternative diagnoses for AD, including

(1) irritant contact dermatitis: which can cause acute or persistent eczematous lesions when an irritant is administered to the site of exposure and may coexist with AD.

(2) Allergic contact dermatitis: is a common rash that appears as an eczematous rash at direct exposure sites. It may spread and coexist with AD.

(3) Seborrheic dermatitis: affects both infants and adults, with a preference for the scalp and napkin area in infants and the scalp, central face, and anterior chest in adults.

(4) scabies, which is common in children with itchy superficial burrows and pustules on palms and soles, between fingers, and on genitalia, might produce secondary eczematous changes,

(5) lichen simplex chronicus: which is common in adults as a result from repetitive scratching or rubbing because of intense itch

(6) asteatotic eczema: which is common in adults with scaly, fissured patches of dermatitis overlying dry skin, and most often on lower legs, and

(7) nummular dermatitis: which is common in children and adults has a coin shaped scaly patches, mostly on legs and buttocks and no itch. [31,32]

CONCLUSION

Dermatitis, sometimes known as eczema, is a prevalent skin disorder affecting millions of individuals around the world. It is characterized by skin inflammation, which causes redness, itching, and discomfort. Dermatitis can be classified into numerous categories, including atopic, contact, seborrheic, and nummular. Dermatitis is caused by a variety of reasons, including exposure to irritant chemicals and scratching, excessive drying, infection of the skin with the yeast *Malassezia furfur*, and high hydrostatic pressure in the veins. It is suggested that you meet with a dermatologist for an accurate diagnosis and treatment options for better skin.

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